

Apêndice 2. Estratégia de busca de acordo com a base de dados.

Base de Dados	Estratégias de Termos/Descritores
PubMed	<p>((“Evidence-Based Pharmacy Practice” OR “Evidence-Based Pharmacy Practices” OR “Pharmacy Practice, Evidence-Based” OR “Pharmacy Practices, Evidence-Based” OR “Practice, Evidence-Based Pharmacy” OR “Practices, Evidence-Based Pharmacy” OR “Evidence-Based Pharmaceutical Care” OR “Care, Evidence-Based Pharmaceutical” OR “Cares, Evidence-Based Pharmaceutical” OR “Evidence Based Pharmaceutical Care” OR “Evidence-Based Pharmaceutical Cares” OR “Pharmaceutical Care, Evidence-Based” OR “Pharmaceutical Cares, Evidence-Based”) OR (“Medication Therapy Management” OR “Management, Medication Therapy” OR “Therapy Management, Medication” OR “Drug Therapy Management” OR “Management, Drug Therapy” OR “Therapy Management, Drug”) OR ("Pharmaceutical Services" OR "Care, Pharmaceutical" OR "Pharmaceutic Service" OR "Pharmaceutic Services" OR "Pharmaceutical Care" OR "Pharmaceutical Service" OR "Pharmacy Service" OR "Pharmacy Services" OR "Service, Pharmaceutic" OR "Service, Pharmaceutical" OR "Service, Pharmacy" OR "Services, Pharmaceutic" OR "Services, Pharmaceutical" OR "Services, Pharmacy")) AND (“Aged” OR “Elderly”) AND (“Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2” OR “Diabetes Mellitus, Type II” OR “Diabetes, Type 2” OR “Type 2 Diabetes” OR “Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus”) AND (“Insulin”)</p> <p>+ filtro de artigos: apenas “Controlled Clinical Trial” and “Randomized Clinical Trial”</p>
BVS	<p>((“Assistência Farmacêutica” OR “Atenção Farmacêutica” OR “Cuidados Farmacêuticos” OR “Serviços Farmacêuticos” OR “Pharmaceutical Care” OR “Pharmaceutical Services” OR “Evidence-Based Pharmacy Practice” OR “Medication Therapy</p>

	<p>Management") AND ("Idoso" OR "Pessoa Idosa" OR "População Idosa" OR "Aged" OR "Elderly") AND ("Diabetes Mellitus Tipo 2" OR "Diabetes Tipo 2" OR "Diabetes Mellitus, Tipo 2" OR "Type 2 Diabetes") AND ("Insulina" OR "Insulin"))</p> <p>+ filtro de artigos: Ensaio clínico controlado</p>
Embase	<p>((("Pharmaceutical Care" OR "Pharmaceutical Services" OR "Evidence-Based Pharmacy Practice" OR "Medication Therapy Management") AND ("Aged" OR "Elderly") AND ("Type 2 Diabetes") AND ("Insulin"))</p> <p>+ 'controlled study'/de OR 'randomized controlled trial'/de)</p>
Cochrane	<p>((("Pharmaceutical Care" OR "Pharmaceutical Services" OR "Evidence-Based Pharmacy Practice" OR "Medication Therapy Management") AND ("Aged" OR "Elderly") AND ("Type 2 Diabetes") AND ("Insulin"))</p> <p>+ Trials</p>